
Scientific Finger Reading Technique

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Summary— The "Scientific Finger Reading Technique" is an innovative educational approach designed to improve children's reading skills through a hands-on, interactive method. Developed by Janilyn P. Beciera, EdD, this technique addresses the prevalent issue of reading difficulties in young learners, which can hinder their academic progress across various subjects. Rooted in the principles of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE), the technique leverages children's native languages to build a strong foundation for acquiring additional languages. The approach involves children using their fingers to trace words, integrating visual and motor skills to enhance comprehension and fluency. This tactile interaction makes reading more engaging and accessible, catering to diverse learning styles. The technique is implemented through a user-friendly digital platform that provides real-time feedback and tracks progress, allowing for targeted interventions and personalized support. The innovation's primary goals are to make reading more enjoyable, foster a positive attitude towards learning, and create inclusive learning environments. The implementation process involves collaboration among educators, parents, and educational specialists, with continuous monitoring and feedback to ensure effectiveness and sustainability. This method aligns with the Department of Education's mission to provide quality education and empower learners, embodying the principles of inclusivity and adaptability.

Keywords— Finger Reading, Interactive, Innovation, Scientific

I. OVERVIEW

Many children face challenges in developing strong reading skills, hindering their overall academic progress. In addition, a research article by (Fleischmann, et al., 2023) do highlight specific and problematic issues when underachieving sections of a classroom are simply left alone without intervention. These challenges create obstacles to achieve the educational outcomes we aim for in our basic education system. A research study entitled "Reading Difficulty and Development of Fluent Reading Skills: An Action Research", stated that Inadequacies in reading skills cause students to fail behind in terms of achievement in both reading and other learning areas (Gedik Akyol, 2022). Addressing these reading challenges can lead to a positive transformation in the educational landscape. Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) is an approach to education where the language or languages that a child already speaks at home are used as a medium of instruction in the early years of schooling. This approach recognizes the importance of a child's mother tongue or first language in learning and aims to build upon that linguistic foundation to facilitate the acquisition of additional languages, including the language of wider communication or instruction. According

to UNESCO (2022) titled " Why Mother Tongue Language-based Education is Essential", MTB is crucial especially in primary school to avoid knowledge gaps and increase the speed of learning and comprehension. Improved reading skills serve as a foundation for success in various subjects, boosting overall academic performance. This, in turn, positively impacts the learners, their families, and the community by creating a more applicable and capable workforce for the future. Scientific Finger Reading Technique directly tackles the identified reading challenges by offering a hands-on and interactive approach. Children use their fingers to trace words, making the reading process more engageable and accessible. This innovation caters to different learning styles, fostering better comprehension and fluency by integrating a simple and effective method,

Scientific Finger Reading Technique contributes significantly to resolve the hurdles in basic education. Aligns seamlessly with the vision and mission of the Department of Education. It contributes to creating a learning environment where students can excel in reading, a fundamental skill for their educational journey. The innovation supports the department's goals of providing quality education and empowering learners to reach their full potential. This innovation perfectly embodies the core principles of inclusivity and adaptability. Ensures that every child, regardless of their learning style, can access the benefits of enhanced reading skills. It serves to advance the goals outlined in the mantra of "Every Child, Every Chance, Every Day" by offering a prac-

tical solution that empowers children success academically and builds a foundation for a lifetime of learning. It simplifies the process, making it easier for children to understand and enjoy reading. By integrating this innovative approach, we are taking a significant step toward ensuring that every child, regardless of their learning style, can access the magic of reading every day. Scientific Finger Reading Technique is not just an innovation; it is a practical tool that embodies our department's commitment to creating inclusive, engaging, and effective learning environments for all children.

II. INNOVATION DESCRIPTION

Scientific Finger Reading Technique is an innovative approach designed to enhance children's reading skills. Why scientific? It's because it provides logic, manipulative, systematic or process to answer and to removes the factors that affects children to read and aim high to reproduce slow reader and even to independent reader as well. The key feature involves a user-friendly interface where children use their fingers to trace words while reading. This interactive method aims to make the reading experience enjoyable and effective. The innovation operates by allowing children to physically trace words with their fingers as they read. This tactile interaction helps in breaking down the reading material into manageable parts, improving comprehension. The innovation emphasizes the connection between visual and motor skills, making the reading process more engaging and memorable for children. In past research conducted by Uhry (1999), they devolved into the advantages of finger-point reading training among kindergartens, highlighting the specific context, limitations, and mental hooks that the kinder learners used when learning reading from scratch. Scientific Finger Reading Technique offers a unique advantage over traditional methods by incorporating a hands-on, interactive element into the learning process. Unlike existing solutions, this innovation caters to different learning styles, providing a personalized and inclusive approach. The simplicity of tracing words with fingers makes it accessible to children of varying ages and abilities, fostering a positive attitude towards reading. The innovation integrates touch-screen technology with proven principles of kinesthetic learning. By leveraging the natural inclination of children to use their fingers, the approach aligns with cognitive learning theories that highlight the importance of physical engagement in the learning process. The technology ensures a seamless and responsive experience, making an effective and efficient tool for improving reading skills. Children able to read with comprehension with their first language or L1 at home or in school as their foundation in reading. This strong foundation makes learning new things in school easier because they already know how to read well. When children feel confident in their first language, they can then learn other languages, like Filipino and English, more quickly and with less difficulty.

III. INNOVATION STATEMENT

The primary goal of introducing Scientific Finger Reading Technique in children is to revolutionize the young minds engage with reading, aiming to enhance their literacy skills and overall educational experience. The innovation seeks to

make reading a more accessible and enjoyable activity for every child, regardless of their learning style or level of proficiency. By leveraging the natural inclination of children to use their fingers, the innovation aims to foster a positive attitude towards reading and promote a lifelong love for learning. The key objectives within the educational context include breaking down the barriers that hinder reading comprehension. By incorporating a tactile and interactive element, the innovation strives to improve word-by-word understanding and overall fluency. The goal is to create an inclusive learning environment, catering to the diverse needs of children and providing a tool that can be easily adopted in various educational settings.

Ultimately, Scientific Finger Reading Technique aspires to contribute to the development of confident and proficient readers, aligning with the broader mission of empowering children to succeed academically and fostering a culture of continuous learning.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION PROCEDURE

a. Process Flow Framework

The steps in the implementation procedure interact seamlessly to facilitate the smooth functioning of Scientific Finger Reading Technique. Each stage builds upon the previous one, creating a continuous learning cycle. Specific methodologies and techniques employed within the process flow include:

1. Selection of Reading Material: The process begins with the selection of appropriate reading material tailored to the children's age and learning level. This step ensures that the content aligns with their interests and educational objectives.
2. Engagement with Demonstration Platform: Children engage with the demonstration platform equipped with Scientific finger-reading technique capabilities. They access the chosen reading material through a user-friendly interface designed for ease of navigation.
3. Tracing Words with Finger: Using their fingers, children trace along the words displayed on the screen while reading. This tactile interaction facilitates a multi-sensory learning experience, enhancing comprehension and retention.
4. Interactive Feedback: The digital platform provides interactive feedback in real-time, responding to the children's finger movements as they trace the words. This feedback mechanism reinforces correct tracing techniques and encourages active participation.
5. Progress Tracking: The platform incorporates progress-tracking features, allowing educators and parents to monitor the children's reading performance over time. This data-driven approach enables targeted interventions and personalized support as needed.
6. Practice and Reinforcement: Children engage in regular practice sessions to reinforce their reading skills using Scientific Finger Reading Technique. Repetition and consistent practice are key elements in solidifying learning outcomes and improving reading fluency.

Fig. 1: Hand Labeling

7. Integration into Learning Environment: Scientific Finger Reading Technique is integrated into the overall learning environment, complementing existing literacy programs and educational initiatives. Educators incorporate this innovative approach into their lesson plans to provide additional support for children’s reading development.

b. Project Management

The management of Scientific Finger Reading Technique involves a collaborative effort among key stakeholders including educators, parents, and education specialists. The coordination and oversight of the project are typically led by a teacher who acts as the central point of contact. The teacher ensures effective communication and collaboration among team members. The main participants of this study are four

Grade II learners from Davao Central District, Division of Davao, with a School ID Number 129560. They were chosen based on the low frequency of their reading-related performance tasks during the first quarter of the academic year 2023-2024. The primary sources of the data and information will be before (second quarter) and after (third quarter) observations. To ensure the successful execution of the innovation, project management employs strategies such as agile methodologies. These methodologies prioritize flexibility and adaptability, allowing the team to respond promptly to feedback and make necessary adjustments to enhance the innovation’s effectiveness. Regular team meetings, progress reviews, and feedback sessions are integral components of the project management approach. The key stakeholders in managing and implementing Scientific Finger Reading Technique include:

- Educators: Responsible for integrating innovation into

Fig. 2: Innovation Process

lesson plans, providing guidance to students, and assessing progress.

- **Parents:** Actively involved in supporting and encouraging their children's engagement with Scientific Finger Reading at home, reinforcing learning outcomes.
- **Principals:** Provide technical expertise in maintaining and updating the demonstration platform, ensuring its functionality aligns with educational objectives.
- **Learners:** Act as active participants in the implementation process, engaging with the Scientific Finger Reading Technique innovation to enhance their reading skills.

c. Timeline

The pre-implementation stage is approximately 2 to 4 weeks. During this phase, activities include comprehensive planning, research on age-appropriate reading materials, and the gathering of necessary resources. The key tasks involve defining educational objectives, selecting the demonstration platform, and establishing communication channels with educators, parents, and principals. The implementation stage is anticipated to unfold over 2 to 3 months, with milestones and key tasks distributed throughout. The initial month focuses on the introduction of Scientific Finger Reading Technique to educators, providing training sessions, and creating awareness about the innovation. Subsequent months involve the gradual integration of Scientific Finger Reading Technique into lesson plan, with checkpoints every week to assess progress. Ongoing training sessions, feedback loops, and regular communication among stakeholders ensure the successful execution of the innovation. The post-implementation phase is design to be continuous, emphasizing ongoing evaluation, refinement, and potential expansion. Monthly evaluations during the first 5 months allow for real-time adjustments, addressing any challenges and optimizing the innovation's impact. After the initial 5-month period, a bi-annual review is conducted to assess the long-term effectiveness and identify opportunities for refinement. The post-implementation phase remains open-ended, encouraging continuous improvement and potential expansion to more classrooms or educational settings based on the success and feedback received during the initial stages. This adaptive approach ensures the sustained success of Scientific Finger Reading Technique in enhancing children's reading skills.

d. Resource Utilization

The creation and operation of Scientific Finger Reading Technique involve a combination of primary resources include:

- **Materials:** Development of age-appropriate reading materials and tactile interfaces for the demonstration platform.
- **Human Capital:** Educators for training and implementation, parents for support, and technology specialists for maintaining the digital platform.

Resource allocation and management are conducted with utmost efficiency throughout the innovation's development and implementation phases. The innovator ensures that materials align with educational objectives, and user-friendly, and human capital is appropriately trained. Regular communication channels and collaborative efforts among educators, parents, and principals streamline resource utilization, preventing inefficiencies and optimizing the overall effectiveness of Scientific Finger Reading Technique. To optimize resource utilization, cost-effectiveness, and sustainability are prioritized. Strategies include:

- **Training Programs:** Efficiently utilizing human capital through targeted training programs for educators and parents ensures they can effectively support and integrate Scientific Finger Reading Technique into the learning environment.
- **Feedback Mechanisms:** Establishing feedback loops allows for continuous improvement based on real-time insights, optimizing both material and human resources to address challenges and enhance effectiveness.

e. Progress Monitoring

Monitoring the progress and outcomes of the innovation falls under the purview of a dedicated monitoring team comprising educators, parent, and principals. Each stakeholder plays a crucial role in ensuring effective oversight and continuous improvement. Educators assess student engagement and learning outcomes, parents provide insights into home usage and children's experiences, while principals oversee the functionality and updates of the demonstration's platform. The progress monitoring process involves a combination of qualitative and quantitative assessments. Educators conduct regular assessments of students' reading skills, tracking improvements, and identifying areas for additional support. Parental feedback is gathered through surveys and regular communication channels to understand the impact of Scientific Finger Reading Technique at home. Principals employ continuous monitoring of the demonstration performance, ensuring its responsiveness and compatibility with evolving educational objectives. Tools and mechanisms for progress monitoring include:

- **Educator Assessments:** Periodic assessments conducted by educators to gauge improvements in students' reading skills.
- **Parental Communication:** Regular surveys and communication channels to gather insights from parents on the impact and effectiveness of Scientific Finger Reading in their children's learning.
- **Demonstrations Platform Analytics:** Principals utilize analytics tools to monitor usage patterns, identify any technical issues, and assess the overall performance of the Scientific Finger Reading Technique demonstration platform.
- **Data Analysis Techniques:** Qualitative and quantitative data analysis techniques are employed to derive actionable insights from assessments, surveys, and platform analytics.

Outputs/Outcomes (Enumerates the outputs or outcomes produced from this innovation)	Beneficiaries 2 females 2 males in Grade Two Durian Sy: 2023-2024
Enhanced Reading Fluency	Learners <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhanced reading fluency and improved comprehension skills contribute to academic success and a positive attitude toward learning.
Improved Comprehension Skills	Parents <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Parents witness increased engagement and enthusiasm for reading in their children, creating a more enjoyable learning experience at home.
Positive Attitude towards Learning	Educators <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Educators observe improved reading outcomes in students, facilitating a more effective and tailored approach to literacy instruction.

Fig. 3: Innovation Output/Outcomes

V. SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

Sustaining the implementation involves establishing ongoing training programs for educators and parents. Regular workshops and refresher courses will ensure that all stakeholders remain proficient in utilizing the innovation effectively. Additionally, continuous creation of new and diverse reading materials will keep the content engaging and relevant. To address potential challenges, a feedback system will be reinforced, encouraging open communication among educators, parents, and technology specialists' Collaborative partnerships with educational researchers will be established to integrate evidence-based practices, ensuring the innovation aligns with the latest advancements in educational technology and pedagogy.

As the innovation continues to be implemented and refined, the desirable outcomes are projected to evolve positively. The sustained engagement of children, measured through increased reading fluency and comprehension, will contribute to a long-term positive impact on their academic journey. Enhanced parental involvement and continued support from educators will further solidify Scientific Finger Reading Technique as a foundational tool for fostering a love for learning and literacy among children, ensuring a

sustained and positive influence on their educational experiences.

REFERENCES

- Fleischmann, M., Hübner, N., Nagengast, B., & Trautwein, U. (2023). The dark side of detracking: Mixed-ability classrooms negatively affect the academic self-concept of students with low academic achievement. *Learning and Instruction*, 86101753.
- Gedik, O., & Akyol, H. (2022). Reading difficulty and development of fluent reading skills: An action research. *International Journal of Progressive Education*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1332254.pdf>
- Uhry, J. K. (1999). Invented spelling in kindergarten: The relationship with finger-point reading. *Reading and Writing*, 11(5-6), 441–464. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1008032502132>
- Unesco. (2022). Why mother language-based education is essential. <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/why-mother-language-based-education-essential>